

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NDIFUNA****FIRST NAME: MOHAMMED****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 100%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The academic essay writing process (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-8)
2. The structure of academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10)
3. American versus British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34)
5. Latin words, expressions, and abbreviations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one has given me a comprehensive introduction to academic writing. Specifically, it has given me an exposition of pertinent concepts and guidelines relating to essay writing, punctuations, writing styles, Latin abbreviations /expressions usage, and sample correction papers. In this response paper, I would like to focus on five concepts raised in the course material; the process of academic essay writing, the structure of academic essays, American versus British English, plagiarism, and the use of Latin words and expressions.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING PROCESS

Academic essay writing may be considered non-fictional writing produced as part of academic work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). Writing is a process with distinct steps. One way is to conceptualize writing as a three-step process: early start-up; defining the question and analyzing the task; drafting an initial plan (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). Dissembling the three basic steps gives rise to many other micro-steps. For instance, it

may consist of 11 basic micro-steps (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8) or even 13 micro-steps (Moxley, n.d.) The writing steps n rigid linear sequencing of the writing tasks (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). Therefore, although the academic writing process is systematic, it is iterative and complex.

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAY

The academic essay is written and structured in a specific way. The basic structure of writing comprises an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10). The Scientific reports follow a format that includes Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion (Adewusi 2021). Since I had had exposure to the IMRAD before the commencement of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course at Euclid University, comparing it to the basic structure was interesting. Both the basic design and IMRAD approach contain the Introduction and conclusion sections. The Methods and Discussion in the IMRAD are analogous to the main body in the basic structure. Another structure for arranging an academic essay comprises the abstract, Introduction, body, discussion, and conclusion (Gardner 2012). The resource pack provided detailed information for each section of the basic structure, which was particularly instructive and brought additional perspectives, clarity of focus, and direction to each section.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

American and British English have equally legitimate claims as versions of English in the global arena and the (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). There are more areas of convergence than divergence. The differences between American and British English are attributable to the unique national histories and cultural contexts under which the two variants (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). Similarly, in other regions, such as Australia, Zealand, South Africa, Canada, and Jamaica, English has morphed with marked accent, diction, and figure of speech differences. In the case of American and British English, the differences observed in pronunciation, spelling, words and their meaning, grammar, usage of collective nouns, and pluralized adjectives, among others (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25–32). English is Standard American English (SAE) or Standard British English (SBE), depending on the extent they adhere to the specific standards. Implicitly this nomenclature acknowledges the existence of variations of English that fall short of the requisite standard. The crux of the matter is that while SAE and SBE are equally correct variations, the writer must select a specific variant of English and then write in accordance standards of the choice. This level of discipline is necessary to avoid confusion, giving offense, appearing too informal when inappropriately judged by other criteria, or facing rejection because it does not conform to the specified guidelines. Therefore, this means that the writer of an academic essay will need to establish the preferred English standard by submitting an article or essay for consideration.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism may occur when the writer fails to give appropriate credit to the source of the words or ideas (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). Intellectual honesty requires the author to recognize thoughts sourced from others, including those from previous work. When an author does not acknowledge his earlier work and passes it off as new ideas in an academic essay, such an author will be guilty of self-plagiarism. Plagiarism is unethical, unfair, and a severe academic offence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). Some strategies to avoid plagiarism include proper citation of the source of the ideas or words used; quotation of the words that have been excerpted from other works and utilized word for word in new academic work; paraphrasing of the ideas generated on the subject in one phrase. Additionally, an academic writer should consider using Software applications such as Grammarly, Turnitin, and Zotero to perform a plagiarism test and ensure proper citation.

6) LATIN WORDS, EXPRESSIONS, AND ABBREVIATION

English appropriates words from other languages (Lee 2010). Subsequently, many Latin words, phrases, or abbreviations are in English and used in academic writing. I recall how frequently I used to apply the expression *Quid pro quo* in Micro Economics and *Actus Reus* in Law essays, respectively, at the undergraduate level of study. It is possible in academic writing to misuse Latin words or expressions. Subsequently, guidance is crucial for academic writers to appreciate the meaning of the relevant words, expressions, abbreviations, and usage rules. For instance, Latin abbreviations are suitable in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing but inappropriate for business, formal, and technical writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59). Using plain language principles in creating content is encouraged (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59). The plain language uses simple words and avoids jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59). In essence, plain language lets the reader decode the written message easily. Preference for simple language does not mean Latin words and their abbreviations are not valuable for academic writing. On the contrary, one should have a good grasp of these words to interact with academic essays that might bear such words or find suitable plain words as substitutes in own writing.

7) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D (Period1) course pack has proven a valuable guide to me by providing me with insight into the process of writing, the structure of essay writing, the ethical challenge of plagiarism and the strategies to avoid it, the different English standards, the usage of Latin words and expressions in academic writing and many other concepts that are outside the scope this response paper. I have also had the opportunity to relate the content in the course pack to other works relevant to the subject in this response paper. As a result of this course, I understand that there are options available to the academic writer, but specific guidelines, conventions, and standards guide each. The

academic writer must adhere to strict ethical standards and avoid plagiarism and have a good command of English grammar and diction consistent with the English language standard preferred.

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